

Energetic Comparison of Rotation and Translation Processes in Magnetic Refrigeration

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Conventional magnetocaloric refrigeration relies on removing a magnetic refrigerant from a magnetic field to induce demagnetization and an adiabatic change in temperature. An emerging alternative, the demagnetizing field-induced magnetocaloric effect (dRMCE), achieves cooling by rotating a shape-anisotropic refrigerant, using changes in the demagnetizing field instead of physical displacement. A key advantage of this approach is its potential for higher energetic efficiency due to reduced work input. This study evaluates that claim by numerically comparing the magnetic work and heat generation in dRMCE and conventional MCE. Using Finite Element analysis, we simulate the demagnetizing field of a thin polycrystalline gadolinium (Gd) plate in both processes, tracking step-by-step energy changes. Our results demonstrate that, despite producing a smaller adiabatic temperature change (ΔT) and less isothermal heat, the dRMCE consistently outperforms conventional MCE in heat-per-work efficiency, exhibiting 20–80% higher efficiency in isothermal demagnetization and 40–80% higher efficiency in adiabatic demagnetization (followed by isomagnetic heating).

Among the countless efforts for reducing greenhouse emissions on multiple sectors, one of great relevance is cooling. It is estimated that 20% of energy usage worldwide is on space cooling¹, which currently relies on compression cycles of greenhouse and ozone-depleting gases. In this context, magnetic refrigeration has become a hot topic of scientific research, with rapid growth since the beginning of the century^{2–4}, promising refrigeration technology that's clean and up to 50% more efficient¹.

Magnetic refrigeration is based on the magnetocaloric effect (MCE), wherein a magnetic refrigerant suffers a change in temperature upon adiabatic magnetization and demagnetization. Conventionally, this is achieved by changing the magnitude of an applied magnetic field by moving the refrigerant out of a permanent magnet or some analogous process³.

An emerging alternative is to take advantage of the demagnetizing field: whenever a magnetic field is applied to a magnetic material, a demagnetizing field H_d opposes the applied field H_0 , such that the internal field becomes $H = H_0 - H_d$. The demagnetizing field depends on the geometry of the refrigerant and its orientation - for example, a thin needle has a lower H_d when pointing in the direction of the field than when pointing perpendicular to it, which is why it naturally points towards an applied magnetic field. By rotating a shape-anisotropic refrigerant, this effect can be harnessed to create a rotating demagnetizing field-induced magnetocaloric effect (dRMCE)^{5–7}, making a promising case of more compact and potentially more efficient magnetic refrigerators. However, this efficiency claim has so far not been verified in the literature. This work takes the first step for assessing this multifaceted engineering problem by analyzing the efficiency of adiabatic and isothermal demagnetization, present in the most popular magnetic refrigeration cycles, namely the Brayton and Ericsson cycles^{3,8}, by considering the magnetic work and absorbed heat of a benchmark magnetic refrigerant, namely a

thin Gadolinium (Gd) plate. The system is modeled as a refrigerant entering (or rotating inside) a Halbach magnet, using the Finite Element method for determining the demagnetizing field, as well as the work required to generate that field and the heat absorbed by the refrigerant in the process.

The magnetic field configuration is the numerical solution to the equation:

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot (\mu(H, T) \nabla u) = 0 \\ \mathbf{H} = -\nabla u, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with boundary conditions:

$$\mathbf{H} \cdot \mathbf{n} \Big|_{\Gamma_{\text{ext}}} = \mathbf{H}_{\text{applied}} \quad (2)$$

where Γ_{ext} is the external boundary of the simulation bounding box. Eq. 1 is a non-linear Poisson equation, and it is solved using the Finite Element method and Newton-Raphson iteration^{9,10}, using the FEMCE software¹¹.

The magnetic permeability $\mu(H, T)$ is a given parameter for the refrigerant material. This work used mean-field data for Gadolinium (Gd) as its source, as used in other works^{12,13}.

This approach is capable of correctly determining the shape and spatially dependent demagnetizing field of a shape-anisotropic refrigerant, which is essential to correctly evaluate the dRMCE. The existence of magnetic domains is not taken into account by the present approach, which would allow an assessment of dynamic losses during field cycling. Nevertheless, a good agreement between experimental magnetization and MCE data can be achieved, as previously reported^{7,14}.

Having determined the H (and B) field in the presence and absence of a magnetic refrigerant enables the calculation of the magnetic work required to magnetize the refrigerant¹⁵:

$$W = \int_{\Omega} \left(\int_{B_r}^B H(B') dB' \right) - \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 H_0^2 d\Omega, \quad (3)$$

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where H_0 is the field in the absence of magnetic material and Ω is the simulation volume. The magnetic force and torque on a particular movement can be calculated by the virtual work principle¹⁶, that is, assuming the refrigerant moves in the x direction:

$$\begin{aligned} F &= -\frac{\partial W}{\partial x}, \\ \tau &= -\frac{\partial W}{\partial \theta}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

and approximated using finite differences (discretizing x and θ).

To validate the work calculations, the experimental results from Balli et al.¹⁷ were reproduced by simulating a $30 \times 20 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ polycrystalline Gd plate at $T_C = 293 \text{ K}$ entering a 2T uniform magnetic field, and comparing the experimental force to our results. Further, using temperature dependent magnetization data, it is possible to simulate the force both under an isothermal and an adiabatic regime. Figure 1 shows both of those results, as well as the experimental data. As expected, the experimental force lies in between the extreme regimes, much closer to adiabatic than isothermal.

FIG. 1. Experimental force from Balli et al.¹⁷ on a Gd plate entering a 2T magnetic field region, compared to simulated results, both in the isothermal and adiabatic regime.

The figures of merit most often used to characterize magnetocaloric materials are the adiabatic temperature change ΔT and the isothermal entropy change ΔS , which can be obtained from the magnetization $M(H, T)$ and specific heat capacity $c_p(H, T)$. For an isothermal demagnetization, the heat absorbed by the refrigerant is $T\Delta S^2$:

$$Q = T \int_{H_{\text{High}}}^{H_{\text{Low}}} \mu_0 \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial T} \right)_{H'} dH'. \quad (5)$$

Another process we simulate is adiabatic demagnetization, followed by isomagnetic heating. In this case, the absorbed heat is:

$$Q = \int_{T_{\text{Cool}}}^{T_{\text{Hot}}} \rho c_p(H, T') dT', \quad (6)$$

where ρ is the refrigerant density. The isothermal process occurs in the Ericsson cycle, whereas the adiabatic one occurs in the Brayton cycle.

For the conventional MCE, the simulation geometry, represented in Figure 2, consists of a $50 \times 3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^3$ rectangular prism as a bounding box, with a $10 \times 1.7 \times 0.05 \text{ cm}^3$ thin, polycrystalline Gd plate as a refrigerant. The magnet is analogous to a Halbach array with 3cm bore diameter and 10cm length, and it is simulated by applying in eq. 2 the condition: $\mu_0 H_{\text{applied}} = 1.2 \text{ T}$ in the z direction on the bore boundary and $\mu_0 H_{\text{applied}} = 0 \text{ T}$ outside the bore boundary. This simulation setup and boundary conditions generate the magnetic field profile represented in figure 3.

FIG. 2. Diagram of the conventional MCE demagnetization. The shaded region represents the bore of a permanent magnet, and the blue rectangular prism is the Gd refrigerant.

In order to simulate the movement of the refrigerant out of the magnet, it is most convenient to move the magnet boundary with a stationary refrigerant rather than the other way around, since this allows the use of a single mesh, with equivalent physics. At each time step, the position of the magnet moves by a certain amount δx , starting at the same position as the refrigerant at $x = 0$, and ending at $x = 15 \text{ cm}$. This final value is chosen to be safely outside of the magnet, with a maximum simulated $\mu_0 H_0$ value below 0.5% of the maximum value of 1.2T, as can be seen in figure 3.

FIG. 3. Simulated magnetic field profile in the bore axis. The shaded region is the inside of the magnet.

In order to simulate the rotating movement, the same bounding box and refrigerant are used, with the same dimensions and position. The only difference is that, instead of

moving the position of the magnet, the direction of the magnetic field is changed instead, in other words, the direction of $\mathbf{H}_{\text{applied}}$ in eq. 2 changes. The demagnetizing field is maximum when the field is perpendicular to the plate (z direction) and minimum when parallel to it (y direction), meaning that the demagnetizing process goes from z to y . This is schematically represented in figure 4.

FIG. 4. Diagram of the simulated demagnetizing field induced rotating magnetocaloric effect (dRMCE) process. The simulation box and magnet bore are the same as in the conventional case.

Both the conventional and rotating movements were simulated at a range of temperatures and fields. Specifically, 32 equally distributed temperatures between 285 K to 302 K, and the applied magnetic fields $\mu_0 H$ are 0.3, 0.75, and 1.2 T.

For an individual simulation at a particular temperature and field, eq. 4 is used to determine the force and torque profile. In figure 5, the force and the torque with $H=1.2$ T and $T=293$ K during adiabatic and isothermal demagnetization are shown.

FIG. 5. Force (left) and torque(right) on the simulation geometry represented in figures 2 and 4 with $H=1.2$ T and $T=293$ K.

The total heat absorbed per unit mass q and a simplistic heat-per-work efficiency figure q/w were evaluated. Figure 6 shows these values for isothermal demagnetization. The values of q are in line with experimental ΔS estimates in the literature⁵, both in the conventional MCE and dRMCE. The dRMCE-generated heat saturates near 0.75T, leaving no advantage in applying higher values of H below the Curie temperature. In contrast, the conventional MCE-generated heat continues to increase with H . The heat-per-work efficiency, however, tells a different story: the amount of work required for the conventional MCE is always significantly larger than

the dRMCE, meaning that q/w is higher in the dRMCE for all values of H and T . Furthermore, in both conventional MCE and dRMCE, q/w is highest near or above T_C , despite the fact that ΔT and q are maximized below T_C in the dRMCE.

FIG. 6. heat-per-work and heat as a function of T and H for Conventional MCE and dRMCE on an isothermal demagnetization process.

In the adiabatic regime (figure 7), the observations are qualitatively similar - in fact, the heat q is almost identical, consistent with the fact that ΔS is the same for both processes (after isomagnetic heating). Numerically, q/w is consistently higher in the adiabatic than in the isothermal regime for the dRMCE, and the gap between the dRMCE and conventional MCE is wider. Notably, the conventional results are almost identical between the adiabatic and isothermal regimes, whereas the dRMCE exhibits significantly higher efficiency in the adiabatic regime.

In more complex device designs, the magnetic work done by the magnetic field during magnetization can be used to balance the work done by the device during demagnetization - for example, Tura et al.¹⁸ uses two AMR beds opposite in phase to achieve this. If done perfectly, this would eliminate most of the magnetic work on the system. While a similar concept can be employed for a dRMCE-based device, we focus on the advantage of the dRMCE to use smaller and simpler designs, as well as motors with less torque

In conclusion, through a magnetic work analysis of demagnetization processes, this study demonstrates that the demagnetizing field-induced magnetocaloric effect (dRMCE) outperforms conventional translation-based MCE in both isothermal (Ericsson cycle) and adiabatic (Brayton cycle) demagnetization processes. Specifically, the rotating process produces 20–80% more cooling per unit work. Based on compar-

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FIG. 7. heat-per-work and heat as a function of T and H for Conventional MCE and dRMCE on an adiabatic demagnetization process.

isons with existing cooling machines¹⁸, we estimate that this improvement could translate to increases above 10% higher system-level efficiency. These results highlight the potential of rotating MCE as a more energy-efficient alternative for magnetocaloric cooling systems.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

H. B. de Souza: Methodology (equal), Software (equal), Formal analysis (lead), Validation (lead), Visualization (lead), Writing - original draft (lead), and Writing - review & editing (support). **R. Kiefe:** Software (equal), Methodology (equal), and Writing - Review & Editing (support). **J. S. Amaral:** Conceptualization (lead), Validation (lead), Data cu-

ration (lead), Funding acquisition (lead), Project administration (lead), Resources (lead), and Writing - review & editing (lead).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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